

Impact of Graphene Currents on Positronium Anion Beam Produced through Internal Photon-Energy Conversion in ^{60}Co and ^{137}Cs Decays

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Development of detection systems such as scintillation crystal/carbon-nanotube bilayer systems is needed for nuclear applications. It allows to clarify the nature of nuclear decays with creation of electron–positron pairs and to search for double electron-capture decays and neutrinoless double β -decay processes for discovering Majorana particles. We design a novel system composed of scintillation crystal NaI(Tl) and carbon-nanotube two-dimensional crystalline layers to record γ -radiation spectra. We perform investigations by means of the developed detector system for exploring interactions between rolled-up graphene walls of carbon nanotubes (CNTs) and ^{60}Co - and ^{137}Cs gamma rays. It was shown that CNT-assembly-enhanced scattering of gamma-rays from Co-60 and Cs-137 decays occurs in an intermediate-size detector NaI(Tl) crystal. A high-performance method based on the enhancement phenomena is offered to detect electron–positron annihilation from cascade events such as nucleus processes of internal energy conversion. We predict and experimentally confirm that the internal conversion in ^{60}Ni nuclei proceeds with generation of positronium ions (P_s^-) and there can appear excited P_s^- states. The excess energy deposition of 3.8–3.9 keV into the detector NaI(Tl)/carbon-nanotube system is evidence of the bound electron–positron pairs from internal energy conversion in nuclei of both ^{60}Ni and $^{137\text{m}}\text{Ba}$.

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1. Introduction

Cascades of γ - and X-ray emissions are an accompanying effect of nuclear decays, and their detection can make it possible to identify rare nuclear processes.

To such events refer phenomena of internal energy conversion, two-neutrino and neutrinoless double beta decays ($2\nu\beta\beta$ and $0\nu\beta\beta$). However, the observation of true coincidence events is often obscured by backscattering in the detector shielding or by the generation of escaping γ - and X-rays within the detector. The random summing

of X-ray pulses of order 10 keV that happens at X-ray generation by γ photons, for example, in high-purity-Ge (HPGe) detectors can be subtracted in multichannel measurements [1]. But, the possibilities of multichannel measurements are significantly reduced in the energy range below 250 keV, where the data reconstruction is weaker due to the backscattering [2]. The recording of $0\nu\beta\beta$ is a challenge of γ -ray time coincidence spectroscopy. In order to identify the $0\nu\beta\beta$ mechanism, which would unveil the Majorana origin of the neutrino and, correspondingly, processes violating the lepton number (L) by two units [3], it is necessary to achieve a considerably higher radiative response than that available in modern nuclear detectors.

Thus, today, ionizing-radiation detectors

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which are capable of recoding so-called escape peaks with high accuracy are much in demand. On the one hand, such development allows to use intermediate-size detectors to design high-performance gamma-ray-radiation spectrometers for prospective nuclear applications; on the other hand, it allows to clarify the nature of nuclear decays with generation of electron-positron pairs (positroniums) and to search for double electron-capture decays and neutrinoless double β -decay processes for discovering Majorana particles [4–6]. Moreover, positronium rays are promising for probing quantum gravity (gravitational acceleration of elementary particles) [7].

In this paper, we explore effects of carbon-nanotube (CNT) graphene walls on energy deposition into detector from incoming ^{60}Co - and ^{137}Cs -gamma rays to assess an neutralizing impact of photon-excited graphene currents on positronium ions which are formed during a process of internal energy conversion in nuclei of ^{60}Ni and $^{137\text{m}}\text{Ba}$. We utilize single-walled carbon nanotube crystalline assemblies (CNT assemblies) to enhance a response of NaI(Tl) detector crystal on gamma-rays from the low-intensity ionized-radiation sources [8–10]. Our goal is to reveal and study an enhancement of scintillation-detector response on ^{60}Co and ^{137}Cs ionizing radiation after an interaction of the gamma-rays with the CNT assemblies. This discovered phenomenon will be employed in the development of a method for effective detection of bound electron-positron pairs by means of such a system as a scintillation crystal NaI(Tl)/CNT bilayer. Furthermore, the interaction of crystalline CNT two-dimensional assemblies with γ -quanta will be studied, and the mechanisms of P_5^- generation in the radiation decay of ^{60}Co will be identified. Our study of all low-intensity events in the ^{60}Co decay is based on the phenomena of CNT-enhanced light scattering.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents and materials

Crystalline bilayers of carbon nanotubes consist of carboxylated and stearic-acid-functionalized single-walled CNTs. These structures have been decorated with nanocyclic complexes of Ce and/or high-spin octahedral Fe, coordinated with ligands of the conducting oligomer 2,5-di(2-thienyl)-1H-pyrrole (2,5-di(2-thienyl)-pyrrole). As a preliminary, an alkyl hydrocarbon chain $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{33}$ was linked chemically to the oligomer. Chemical formula of the oligomer has the following form: 3-hexadecyl-2,5-di(thiophen-2-yl)-1H-pyrrole (H-DTP). A 5-monolayer graphene-like film of the nanocyclic organometallic complexes is fabricated by means of the Langmuir–Blodgett (LB) nanotechnology. At first, the five monolayers of the nanocyclic organometallic complexes have been deposited on the interdigital structure of aluminium electrodes, on the surface of which a layer of nanoporous anodic alumina (AOA) have been previously formed as a insulator coating. Then, inverse micelles of stearic acid with CNTs inside have been obtained by mixing stearic acid and CNTs in hexane by the ultrasound treatment. Thereafter, a 2-monolayer LB film being fabricated from these micellar CNTs by the LB technique is deposited on the nanocyclic-complex LB-cover.

Standardized (reference) Co-60 and Cs-137 low-intensive ionized-radiation sources (IRSs) were utilized as radioactive materials. Activities of radioactive decay of ^{137}Cs (CsI) and ^{60}Co IRSs were of 62.2 and 28.1 kBq, respectively, at the moment of irradiation.

The radiation of low-intensive beta-particles beam has been ttenuated by a thin-film aluminium screen. The IRSs have the form of a drop with a mean diameter about $d = 1.5$ mm. A sample with a diameter $D_s = 4$ mm was exposed through a lead collimator of a 5 mm diameter and 25-, 50-mm length. The IRSs were placed above the collimator. At the ratio $d/L = 0.03, 0.06$, the IRS can be considered a point source. A gamma-

radiation fluence rate in the irradiated sample can be estimated as

$$\phi_0 = \frac{kA_t \pi D_s^2}{4L^2 4L^2}$$

where k is the percentage of the emitted photons per one decay (quantum yield), $\frac{\pi D_s^2}{4L^2}$ is the solid angle under which the irradiated sample is viewed from the point IRS.

2.2. Methods

2.2.1. Exposure to radiation

The irradiation geometry was arranged to be parallel through the use of a point source, when one can neglect the processes of electron-positron pair production in the surrounding materials. Otherwise, an annihilation peak could be registered, which is typical one for detectors with 4π geometry [20]. A sample with a diameter $D_s = 4$ mm is exposed through a collimator being of the order of 5 mm in diameter and $L = 50$ mm long. At ratio $d/L = 0.03$ and 0.06 , IRS can be considered as a point source.

2.2.2. Radiation spectroscopy

Analysis of secondary electrons spectra has been performed by a lab-quality radiation spectrometric facilities "Nuclear Physics" (BSU, Minsk, Belarus). The scintillation crystal thallium-activated sodium iodide, NaI(Tl) (a diameter of 25 mm, a height of 40 mm) was utilized as a detector crystal. Channel number is proportional to the impulse height.

3. Results

3.1. Intermediate-size-detector responses to photon beams of ^{60}Co decay and detector calibration

Exploiting the detector crystal during a recording time, Δt_{bg} , in the presence of a sample

comprised of single-walled-CNT assemblies only, we have detected a radiation background, R'_{bg} , and then its count rate, R_{bg} , (counts per one minute in a channel) equal to $R_{bg} = R'_{bg}/\Delta t_{bg}$ with $\Delta t_{bg} = 30$ min was evaluated. The detector-response R'_{Co} was recorded during the entire 46-minute irradiation of the detector crystal. The R_{bg} was subtracted from a detector-response rate $\frac{R'_{Co}}{\Delta t_{Co}}$ (radiation spectrum) for the ^{60}Co -IRS photon beam incoming through the pure collimator (without the single-walled-CNT assemblies) during the $\Delta t_{Co}=46$ min. Violet "0" and yellow diagrams from Figs. 1a–b and 1c, respectively, depict the $R_{Co} \equiv \frac{R'_{Co}}{\Delta t_{Co}} - R_{bg}$ and the low-intensity R_{bg} , respectively.

The linear conversion of the pulse height (channel number) N into the energy $E : N \rightarrow E/a$ was performed with non-zero offset b . The calibration coefficients were calculated by taking energies, E_0 and E_k , for the emitted photon and the Compton edge, respectively, as

$$E_0 = aN_0 + b; \quad E_k = aN_k + b. \quad (3.1)$$

The Compton edge E_k is determined by the following formula:

$$E_k = E_0 \{1 - [1 + 2E_0/(m_e c^2)]^{-1}\}. \quad (3.2)$$

Here c is the light speed, m_e is the electron mass. A ^{60}Co -decay gamma ray deposits the energy of $E_0 = 1173.21$ keV in the channel of $N_0 = 574$ and an escaping γ -ray being the 1173.2-keV photon after the single Compton scattering at the angle 180° , deposits the energy $E_k = 963.1$ keV in the detector channel of $N_k = 471$. The full-energy peak (photopeak) at the energy of 1173.2 keV is marked as $Ph_{1173.21}$. The coefficients of calibration over the two gamma-rays are with the following values:

$$a = 2.04, b = 2.35. \quad (3.3)$$

The calibration (3.3) gives that the gamma-ray photopeak " $Ph_{1332.43}$ " is detected by the NaI(Tl)-crystal detection system in the 652th channel with the energy of 1332.43 keV. The

FIG. 1. (Color online) (a) The pulse-counting rate in the channel both for ^{60}Co -IRS (response function “0” presented in magenta color) and the CNT-bilayer-sample/ ^{60}Co system. The diagram “0” in magenta color presents the response of the NaI(Tl) detector on the ^{60}Co -decay γ radiation at simultaneous 46-min exposure and 46-min recording, while the response function “4” presented in dark-blue color was recorded after 86-min exposure during 34 min simultaneously with the additional 34-min exposure. (b) Inset to the figure (a). All radiation spectra were obtained by subtracting the background-radiation spectrum shown in the figure (c) from the recorded responses. Two photopeaks from the ^{60}Co decay, single Compton edge of the 1.332-MeV- γ -ray single Compton continuum, and coincidence summing peaks are labeled by $Ph_{1173.21}$ and $Ph_{1332.43}$, “1.332-MeV Single Compton Edge”, and “Coincidence Sum Peak 1” and “Coincidence Sum Peak 2”; a single Compton edge of the 1.173-MeV- γ -ray single Compton continuum is marked as “Single Compton Edge”; escaping absorber-scattered annihilation photons deposit energy in channels which are denoted by “Double escape”, “Single escape”, “Low-energy P_S^- ”, and “High-energy P_S^- ”; peaks attributed to vortical CNT defects are denoted by V_{ch} , V_{sc} , and V_{nc} ; peaks “Brem” and “BS” are attributed to bremsstrahlung process and Compton backscattering in materials surrounding the detector, respectively.

1.332-MeV photon scattered at the angle of 180° deposits 1118.23 keV in the 547th channel (see Fig. 1). The 1.332-MeV-photon Compton edge is very close to the prediction of 1118.01-keV energy by using the formula (3.2) that confirms fidelity of the calibration. Thus, the detector is calibrated very good.

Among with the two photopeaks, single and multiple Compton scattering events, labeled as “Single Compton” and “Multiple Compton”, which are attributed to the responses of the intermediate-size scintillation detector for the ^{60}Co IRS (see Figs. 1a–b) there are other peaks also. Among them, low-intensity events were recorded against the background of the single Compton continuum. (see Figs. 1a–b). The γ -photon scattering in the lead (Pb) shield gives rise to a larger backscatter peak “BS” (see Figs. 1a–b). Using the calibration, we obtained X- and gamma-ray energies for the all peaks of the recorded radiation spectra. The calculated energies are presented by Table 1.

3.2. CNT-enhanced deposition of ^{60}Co -decay energy in scintillation detector

The background radiation was subtracted from CNT-bilayer/NaI(Tl) radiation responses R'_{CoG_4} were recorded after 86-minute CNT-bilayers exposure to γ rays from ^{60}Co decay. The spectrum was recorded during the subsequent 34 minutes with simultaneous irradiation. Figs. 1a–b depicts the detector response rate, $R_{CoG_4} \equiv \frac{R'_{CoG_4}}{\Delta t_{CoG_4}} - R_{bg}$ where $\Delta t_{CoG_4} = 34$ min is the time for recording the radiation spectra. As is seen from a comparison between peak intensities, an enhancement of the radiation scattering occurs in the CNT bilayer/NaI(Tl) detection system. The phenomenon of CNT-enhanced scattered ^{60}Co radiation will be studied further.

The count rate for the two photopeaks recorded by the NaI(Tl)/CNT detector system is enhanced by about 2 (compare the detector responses, R_{Co} and R_{CoG_4} shown in Figs. 1a–b). The enhancement effect depends on the time of

sample irradiation and the enhancement extent grows with the increase of the irradiation time.

The intensity of the 1.332-MeV-photon single Compton edge in the violet spectrum “0” being recorded by the pure detector crystal is very weak. The enhancement of the single Compton edge this single Compton edge prominent in the response R_{CoG_4} (make comparison between radiation spectra R_{CoG_4} and R_{Co} in Fig. 1b). Coincidence Sum Peaks 1 and 2 appear due to true coincidence summing of pulses from two 616.39-keV photons and from 693.91- and 516.43-keV gamma-ray interactions, respectively. The 616.39- and 693.91-keV annihilation peaks are marked as “High-energy P_S^- ” and the 516.43-keV peak is labeled by “Low-energy P_S^- ” (see Figs. 1a–b). The peaks “High-energy P_S^- ” “Low-energy P_S^- ” in the spectrum R_{CoG_4} are prominent events recoded against a background of the single Compton scattering.

Further, we will explore lower-intensity events in the ^{60}Co decay. The investigation is based on the enhancement of radiation response from CNT/NaI(Tl) system.

3.3. Cascade events and internal conversion of entangled-state energy in ^{60}Co nucleus decay

The (true) coincidence summing events (“Coincidence Sum Peak 1” and “Coincidence Sum Peak 2” presented in Table 1) give evidence of the fact that there are cascade events. Such events include the process of the internal energy conversion in nuclei, when a virtual photon, γ_1 , creates an electron–positron pair, $e^+ - e^-$, as a K -shell electron appears in the nucleus. The probability of residence in the excited ^{60}Ni nucleus for the K -shell electron is high due large sizes of the excited states.

Generally speaking, since ^{60}Co is not a β^+ -ray emitter, there should exist positronium-like configurations comprised of one positron and one or two electrons, when the positron attracts one or two electrons, respectively. It means that the

Table 1. Maximal channel numbers for the characteristic peaks in the response rates R_{Co} and ΔR_{CoG} of NaI(Tl) crystal detector and CNT-bilayer/NaI(Tl) detector system, respectively, on ^{60}Co radiation; irradiation times are of 46 and 120 min for NaI(Tl) and CNT/NaI(Tl), respectively.

Name of peak	R_{Co} , number /keV	ΔR_{CoG} , number /keV	Assignment
X	71/ 147.19	61/ 126.79	Characteristic hard X-ray resulting from an internal conversion; 120–130-, 123.6- keV X-ray recorded by CdZnTe [21], Si(Li) [22] detectors, respectively
$Brem$	85	85	Bremsstrahlung process at 175.75 keV
$Ph_{1332.4}$	652/ 1332.43	642	Photoelectric absorption of 1332.43-keV gamma ray
$Ph_{1173.21}$	574/ 1173.2	570	Photoelectric absorption of 1173.21-keV gamma ray
BS	110/ 226.75	110	Compton backscattering at 200–250 keV [17, 23] in materials surrounding the detector
V_{ch}	–	187	Production of chiral vortex pair
V_{sc}	–	483	Production of semi-chiral vortex pair
V_{nc}	–	520	Production of non-chiral vortex pair
$Single\ Compton$	208– 471 / 426.67– 963.1	228– 454	Single Compton continuum scattering of 1.173-MeV photon, the first Single Compton edge is of 963 keV [23]
$1.332\text{-MeV}\ Single\ Compton\ Edge$	547/ 1118.23	545/ 1114.15	1.332-MeV-photon Compton edge at 1117 [21], 1131.8 and 1118.44 [16] keV for CdZnTe, NaI(Tl) and HPGe detectors, respectively
$Single\ escape$	401	401	Single-escape peak at 826.06 (NaI(Tl) detector [13, 15]), 817.6 (HPGe detector [16]), 820.39 (our result) keV for 1.332-MeV photon
$Double\ escape$	151	151	Double-escape peak at 347 (NaI(Tl) detector [13, 15]), 306 (HPGe detector [16]), 310.39 (our result) keV for 1.332-MeV photon
$Low\text{-energy}\ P_S^-$	251/ 514.39	252/ 516.43	Destruction of positronium-anion low-energy excited state; the 510.86-keV peak recorded by a NaI(Tl) detector in [18]
$High\text{-energy}\ P_S^-$	301/ 616.39	339/ 693.91	Destruction of positronium-anion high-energy excited state; the 619.56-keV peak in NaI(Tl)-detector response on ^{60}Co radiation [18]
$Coincidence\ Sum\ Peak\ 1$	603/ 1232.47	n/a	True coincidence summing of pulses from two 616.39-keV positronium-destruction photons
$Coincidence\ Sum\ Peak\ 2$	n/a	592/ 1210.03	True coincidence summing of pulses from 693.91- and 516.43-keV positronium-destruction photons

K -shell electron, $e_{K-shell}^-$, attracts the positron. When forming the positronium configuration, the positron, e^+ , $e^+ - e^-$ is linked with $e_{K-shell}^-$. After colliding with a virtual γ_2 ray, the e^- from the $e^+ - e^-$ pair can be caught by the positron being in the bound state. When both e^+ and $e_{K-shell}^-$ are resident on a same energy level, E_m , their spins are parallel to each other due to a Pauli principle, and the electron e^- being on an excited energy level, E_n , possesses any spin direction (“up” or

“down”). The three-body system is charged.

3.3.1. A virtual positronium production

For a forbidden nuclear transition to occur during ^{60}Co decay from the third or second excited ^{60}Ni states with multipolarity “4+” or “2+”, respectively, to states with multipolarity “2+” or “0+”, respectively, two virtual gamma

rays, $\gamma_i^v, i = 1, \dots, 2$, should be emitted by ^{60}Ni to satisfy the law of angular momentum conservation. Virtual electron–positron pairs with spins “1” and “0” should be generated by these γ_1^v and γ_2^v in an electrical field of external electron, $e_{\uparrow, E_0, K\text{-shell}}^-$, from, for example, the atomic K shell. Both the emerging positronium states, ortho- P_S ($e_{\uparrow, E_0}^+ - e_{\uparrow, E_1}^-$) with spin “1” and para- P_S ($e_{\uparrow, E_0}^+ - e_{\downarrow, E_1}^-$) with spin “0”, enter a positronium-ion beam that is formed by following two configurations:

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(e_{\uparrow, E_0}^+ - e_{\uparrow, E_0, K\text{-shell}}^- - e_{\downarrow, E_1}^- \right) \\ & + \left(e_{\uparrow, E_0}^+ - e_{\uparrow, E_0, K\text{-shell}}^- - e_{\uparrow, E_1}^- \right) \end{aligned} \quad (3.4)$$

as the P_S^- ray appears in ground state after mixing the ortho- P_S and para- P_S . In accordance with the Pauli principle, both the positron $e_{E_0}^+$ and the electron $e_{E_0, K\text{-shell}}^-$ possess spins “up” at the zero-energy level, E_0 , and the electron $e_{\uparrow(\downarrow)}^-$ resides

at the energy level E_1 for the negatively charged positronium state being in the ground state with the lowest energy. Fig. 2a, up presents a diagram of energy levels for the P_S^- ground state. An energy of the bound electron-positron pair less than $2mc^2$ for the $\gamma_i, i = 1, 2$ with the energy smaller than $2mc^2$.

A superposition of γ_1 and γ_2 photons is created by an interaction between two virtual electron–positron pairs. Fig. 2b presents a diagram as such the interaction. Two electron (positron) and positron (electron) loops, comprised of electron and positron propagators (Green functions) with counterclockwise and clockwise orientations, respectively, may be arranged both in the plane XY , orthogonal to the axis Z , and in the plane parallel to Z . Calculation of the diagram produces a polarization for the mixing P_S state and is therefore capable of presenting the wave function Ψ_{mix} as

$$\Psi_{mix, P_S} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left[\psi_{e^+ - e^-, l, \parallel} \psi_{e^+ - e^-, r, \parallel} + (e^{i\Phi_1} \psi_{e^+ - e^-, r, \perp}) (e^{i\Phi_2} \psi_{e^+ - e^-, l, \perp}) \right] \quad (3.5)$$

where $\psi_{e^+ - e^-, l, \parallel(\perp)}$ and $\psi_{e^+ - e^-, r, \parallel(\perp)}$ are wave functions of bound electron–positron pairs whose electric dipole moments rotating counterclockwise (left-rotating) and clockwise (right-rotating), respectively, in the plane parallel (orthogonal) to Z ; Φ_1 and Φ_2 are phases added at the rotation by the angle $(\pi/2)$.

As one can see, the P_S^- ground state is a virtual one because the electron e_{\uparrow, E_1}^- , after annihilating the zero-energy pair $(e_{\uparrow, E_0}^+ - e_{\uparrow, E_0, K\text{-shell}}^-)$, returns to the state with spin “ \downarrow ”, and not to the initial state with spin “ \uparrow ”, which is forbidden by the law of angular momentum conservation. Thus, a generation of electron in the internal conversion of excited-nucleus energy does not be permitted for the virtual γ photons when creating P_S^- being in the

ground state.

3.3.2. Entanglement and high-energy positronium-ion generation

Now, let us prove that entanglement of virtual photons is a necessary condition for such cascade events as an internal energy conversion followed by positronium-ion production.

For higher photon energies, for example, for 1.332 MeV, the positron e_{\uparrow}^+ and the electron $e_{\uparrow, K\text{-shell}}^-$ with the E_0 energy may be excited to higher energy levels only because the Pauli principle forbids transitions from the ground state to the E_1 level and permits that such a

configuration as

$$\begin{aligned} & \left(e_{\uparrow, E_2}^+ - e_{\uparrow, E_0, K-shell}^- - e_{\uparrow, E_1}^- \right) \\ & + \left(e_{\uparrow, E_0}^+ - e_{\uparrow, E_2, K-shell}^- - e_{\downarrow, E_1}^- \right) \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

is a virtual only. The P_S^- state (3.6) is shown in Fig. 2a. Since the bound electron–positron pairs possess an energy less than for free electron–positron pairs the P_S^- state (3.6) is permitted by the law of energy conservation also and therefore is a physical one. The K -shell electron in the transition of the P_S^- ray from the excited to the ground state, and after annihilation of the pair ($e^+ - e^-$), may acquire additional energy and leave the atom as a conversion electron; upon its return to the initial level, X-rays are emitted, designated as an atomic-shell line in a radiation spectrum.

Since spins of both the electron–positron pairs $(e_{\downarrow, E_1}^+ - e_{\uparrow, E_1}^-)$ and $(e_{\uparrow, E_0}^+ - e_{\downarrow, E_1}^-)$ are equal to zero the double rotation at an angle

of $\frac{\pi}{2}$ gives the same wave function and, correspondingly, the wave function (3.5) at $\Phi_1 = \Phi_2 = \Phi$ becomes the following wave function of the P_S ray with spin “0”:

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi_{mix, P_S} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \left(\psi_{e_{\uparrow}^+ - e_{\downarrow}^-, l, \parallel} \psi_{e_{\downarrow}^+ - e_{\uparrow}^-, r, \parallel} \right. \\ & \left. + e^{2i\Phi} \psi_{e_{\uparrow}^+ - e_{\downarrow}^-, r, \perp} \psi_{e_{\downarrow}^+ - e_{\uparrow}^-, l, \perp} \right). \end{aligned} \quad (3.7)$$

The two interacting pairs $(e_{\downarrow, E_2}^+ - e_{\uparrow, E_0}^-)$ and $(e_{\uparrow, E_0}^+ - e_{\downarrow, E_2}^-)$ include the electrons bound with positrons and when turning on the left or right along the corresponding loops and therefore possessing oscillating electrical dipole moments generate circularly left- and right-hand polarized electromagnetic quanta γ_1 and γ_2 . Then the wave function (3.7) brings out a two-photon wave function for the superposition consisting of γ_1 and γ_2 as

$$\Psi^{entangled\gamma} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left[\psi_{\gamma_1, l, \parallel} \psi_{\gamma_2, r, \parallel} + (e^{i\Phi} \psi_{\gamma_1, r, \perp}) (e^{i\Phi} \psi_{\gamma_2, l, \perp}) \right]. \quad (3.8)$$

because the circularly polarized γ -quanta with oppositely directed spins form a linearly polarized photon beam with spin “0” and, correspondingly, the two-photon beam satisfies the law of angular-momentum conservation. The superposition (3.8) is generated by the two-photon beams, $\psi_{\gamma_1, l, \parallel} \psi_{\gamma_2, r, \parallel}$ and $\psi_{\gamma_1, r, \perp} \psi_{\gamma_2, l, \perp}$, with polarization planes orthogonal and parallel to an axis Z , respectively, and, correspondingly, with photon spins, s , rotated on zero and $\frac{\pi}{2}$ angles, respectively:

$$\begin{aligned} \Psi^{entangled\gamma} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} & \left[\psi_{\gamma_1, l, \parallel} \psi_{\gamma_2, r, \parallel} \right. \\ & \left. + \left(e^{i\pi/2} \psi_{\gamma_1, r, \perp} \right) \left(e^{i\pi/2} \psi_{\gamma_2, l, \perp} \right) \right]. \end{aligned} \quad (3.9)$$

Here the added phase angle of $\frac{\pi}{2}$ appears because the rotation of the electric field strength, \vec{E} , of

the electromagnetic wave twice by the angle of $\frac{\pi}{2}$ is equivalent to a shift of the electromagnetic-wave phase by π . The two-photon beam (3.9) formed by two circularly polarized γ -quanta with oppositely directed spins is a linearly polarized one and, correspondingly, the para- P_S is created by a linearly polarized electromagnetic beam. The entanglement (3.9) is confirmed experimentally (see [24] and references therein). The dipole electric moment may rotate under the action of a third circularly polarized gamma ray and, correspondingly, the three gamma rays generate a positronium with spin “1”.

Thus, we have prove that the two high-energy P_S^- -annihilation events in the internal energy conversion should appear simultaneously in true coincidence. De-excitation of high-energy

FIG. 2. (Color online) (a) A sketch of internal high-energy conversion. (b) A cartoon of photons entanglement along two polarization loop.

positronium state precedes the annihilation of the bound electron–positron pair. The de-excitation is depicted on Fig. 2. The de-excited state is one of the two high-energy excited positronium ions after emitting an electromagnetic ray, “X”, with the energy E_{X-ray} transits from the state

$$\left(e_{\uparrow, E_2}^+ - e_{\uparrow, E_0, K-shell}^- - e_{\uparrow, E_1}^- \right) \quad (3.10)$$

into the state

$$\left(e_{\downarrow, E_1}^+ - e_{\downarrow, E_0, K-shell}^- - e_{\downarrow, E_0}^- \right). \quad (3.11)$$

The de-excitation process is pictured in Fig. 2a.

The photons produced by the annihilation of the low- and high-energies excited P_S^- states

should appear coherently due to the entanglement (3.9) of virtual photons generating these P_S^- . It means that if a positron is extracted from any one positronium-ion, it nevertheless remains entangled with another P_S^- and, correspondingly, in essence, the extraction does not occur from an isolated positron, but from such a superposition as

$$e^+ - P_S^- \equiv 2e^+ + 2e^-. \quad (3.12)$$

An emergence of only positronium anions P_S^- without P_S from a positron/ P_S^- (e^+/P_S^-) converter (only subsequently, laser photo-detachment of the P_S^- ions forms a long-lived ortho- P_S beam) [25, 26]. is as an experimental

confirmation for the predicted entangled two-positronium-ion configuration (3.7).

The coincidence summing peaks at 603th (at the energy of 1232.47 keV) and 592th (at the annihilation energy of 1210.03 keV) channels of NaI(Tl) detector and CNT/NaI(Tl) detector system, respectively, (see Table 1 and Fig. 1b) are a signature of the two P_S^- entangled configurations. Our model of internal energy conversion predicts that an interaction between P_S^- and graphene currents causes a transition of e_{\uparrow}^+ from the E_0 energy level to the level E'_1 with subsequent generation of the bound electron-positron pair ($e_{\downarrow, E'_1}^+ - e_{\downarrow, E'_1}^-$). It means that the P_S^- energy is decreasing by an energy gap, E_{gap} , of the pair $e_{\downarrow, E'_1}^+ - e_{\downarrow, E'_1}^-$. We can make an assessment of E_{gap} based on the converted energy, E_{γ} , of 1.332-MeV γ ray deposited by the annihilation of both high- and low-energy P_S^- and by the X ray in the channels of CNT/NaI(Tl) system as

$$E_{\gamma} = E_{high-energy-P_S^-} + E_{low-energy-P_S^-} + E_{X-ray} - E_{gap} = 1332.43 \text{ keV.} \quad (3.13)$$

Now, we perform a following averaging for $E_{low-energy-P_S^-}$: $\langle E_{low-energy-P_S^-}^{exper} \rangle \approx 515.41 \text{ keV}$ and take rounded values of $\langle E_{X-ray}^{exper} \rangle = 126.8$ and $\langle E_{high-energy-P_S^-}^{exper} \rangle = 694 \text{ keV}$ for E_{X-ray} and $E_{high-energy-P_S^-}$, respectively, to estimate the energy gap entering (3.13) as (in keV)

$$E_{gap} = \langle E_{low-energy-P_S^-}^{exper} \rangle + \langle E_{high-energy-P_S^-}^{exper} \rangle + \langle E_{X-ray}^{exper} \rangle - 1332.43 = 3.8. \quad (3.14)$$

Thus, the energy excess of 3.8 keV arises after generation of the pair $e_{\uparrow, E'}^+ - e_{\uparrow, E'}^-$ as a work is performed by a neutralizing force exerted on the P_S^- in graphene.

3.3.3. Conversion electrons and formation of low-energy unstable bound electron-positron pairs

Effectively, an electron-positron pair ($e_{\uparrow, E_0}^+ - e_{\uparrow, -E_0 > 0}^-$) with spin "1" due the angular-

momentum conservation law and with zero energy is produced by one of two virtual γ_1^v and γ_2^v , for example, by γ_1^v , in an electrical field of external electron, $e_{\uparrow, E_0, K-shell}^-$. When satisfying the energy conservation law the bound pair $e_{\uparrow, E_0}^+ - e_{\uparrow, E_0, K-shell}^-$ with zero energy can be located on the energy level E_0 and then is linked with an electron $e_{\uparrow(\downarrow), E_1}^-$ from a second pair $e_{\uparrow(\downarrow), E_1 < 0}^+ - e_{\uparrow(\downarrow), -E_1 > 0}^-$ which is produced by the second virtual photon γ_2^v . The proposed model of internal conversion of gamma-photon energy into the energy of the positronium anion P_S^- is depicted on Fig. 3.

The positron e'^+ annihilates with the electron e'^- after radiating a real γ quant, $\gamma_{\Delta E}$, possessing an energy being of the difference, $\delta E = E_1 - E_0$, of the e'^- and e'^+ energies. The $\gamma_{\Delta E}$ excites the positron e_{\uparrow, E_0}^+ from the E_0 level into the energy level E_1 ; then e_{\uparrow, E_1}^- for satisfying the Pauli principle transits immediately from the E_1 level into the energy level E_0 . However, the transition of e^+ into the energy level E_1 entails a simultaneous transition of $e_{K-shell}^-$ into the energy level E_1 because the atom Fermi statistics which allows location of two electrons for the same level prevents destruction of the link between e^+ and $e_{K-shell}^-$. The state of

$$e_{\downarrow, E_1}^+ - e_{\downarrow, E_1, K-shell}^- - e_{\downarrow, E_0}^- \quad (3.15)$$

becomes physical one because the spin flip precedes the pair annihilation and, correspondingly, the angular momentum conservation law is not broken. The two-level diagram and the scheme of the spin-dependent level filling for the low-energy positronium-anion production is shown in Fig. 3b. Electron- and positron-density distributions are the same and therefore unstable as the two bound electron-positron pairs created by the two virtual γ rays are resident on the ground and 1st energy levels. Every one of these two P_S^- configurations is generated by the entangled γ_i^v ray, $i = 1, 2$. When the unstable electron-positron pairs disappears the electron e_{\downarrow, E_1}^- called as a conversion electron becomes free and is immediately ejected from nucleus.

FIG. 3. (Color online) (a) A cartoon of internal conversion of γ -photon energy into the energy of the bound electron–positron pair (positronium) and the energy of an electron from the K -shell; black dots denote Feynman diagrams, \curvearrowright , for virtual electron–positron pairs annihilating to gamma rays. Protons and neutrons are depicted as orange and sage-green balls, respectively. The electron from K shell and the electron from the electron–positron pair are depicted as blue and magenta circles, the positron is depicted as a green circle. (b) Low-energy excitation of positronium anion: energy level diagrams for P_S^- in ground state (left), in an entangled excited two-level state (right, up), and (right, down) a superposition arising from the two excited states under the neutralizing impact of graphene currents. Graphene vortex hole and electron are in brown and yellow, respectively; spins of particles are imaged by arrays.

Thus, in the virtual process, the bound positron is linked to the pair electron after colliding with the second gamma photon to be captured. The internal conversion of nuclear energy into positronium energy changes the nuclear spin (angular momentum) by 1 (transition multipolarity of 1) when the particles spins from the electron–positron pair are in same directions. The two virtual gamma rays must be at true coincidence of their emission for the ^{60}Ni nuclear transition with multipolarity “2”. Since the atom remains neutral the law of electric-charge conservation forbids the departure of an electron into the Dirac sea until double

β -ray-capture processes with annihilation occur. The positron does not interact with a neutron also until neutrinoless double β -decay processes happen. The internal conversion of photon energy into energy, $E_{3\beta}$, of positron linking two negative β rays can occur due to the fact that the positronium rest state is long-living. The system consisting of three β rays is a positronium ion (positronium anion, P_S^-).

Further, we give evidence that the internal conversion of photon energy into energy of system consisting of three β -rays can cause the appearance both of the K -line and the smaller peaks “Low-energy P_S^- ” and “High-energy P_S^- ”.

Energy of $e_{K-shell}^-$ binding is chosen as a K -shell-electron binding energy, $E_{bind,shell}$, for ^{60}Co due to virtuality of the process.

3.4. Radiation spectral analysis of escaping absorber-scattered gamma rays

The other radiations can include 1) annihilation photons appearing due to an electron–positron pair production [28] and 2) X rays produced by electron captures or internal conversion processes proceeding in excited nuclei [11, 12].

The 1022–1118.01-keV photons of single Compton continuum (see Table 1) can produce an electron–positron pair in an electrical field of electron or nucleus. As a result, the 1.332-MeV-photon single Compton edge falls down. The lack of photon number explains the facts that the intensity of the 1.332-MeV-photon single Compton edge lower than the 1.173-MeV-photon Compton edge and is observed as a shoulder of the 1173.2-MeV photopeak in the radiation spectrum R_{Co} in violent color (see Fig. 1b).

As can be seen from Figs. 1a–b and Table 1, the detector response on the IRS radiation indicates the two smaller escape annihilation peaks labeled as “Single escape” and “Double escape”. The annihilation peaks appear at energies 510.99 and 1.022 MeV below the 1.332-MeV photopeak and, correspondingly, give evidence that one or both annihilation photons escape from the detector crystal. But, such annihilation photons from the 1.173-MeV pair production and, correspondingly, “1.173-MeV *Single escape*” and “1.173-MeV *Double escape*” peaks in the ^{60}Co -decay radiation response are absent in the detector response.

An experimental peak “ X ” appears at the energy of $E_{K-line}^{exper} = 147.19$ keV deposited in 71-th channel of the ^{60}Co -radiation response, R_{Co} (see Figs. 1a–b and Table 1). The peak in the radiation spectra could be from a (true) coincidence event happening due to an interaction between the MeV γ photons and electrons from

K -shells of Pb or ^{60}Co atoms and a subsequent creation of electron–positron pairs in the electric field. It means that the experimental peak “ X ” could originate from the K line which stems from internal conversion of 1.173- and 1.332-MeV gamma rays energy into the nucleus energy.

The sum “kinetic energy”, E_{kin}^{exper} , for the electron and positron from the pair produced by 1.173-MeV photon is equal to (in keV)

$$E_{kin}^{exper} = 1173 - E_{K-line}^{exper} - 2m_e c^2 \approx 3.8. \quad (3.16)$$

The small kinetic energy (~ 1.9 keV) of the positron created by the 1.173-MeV gamma photon would be sufficient for the positron to reach ^{60}Co -IRS or Pb-shield surface with subsequent annihilation, however it does not happen. Moreover, neglecting the fact of high energy equal to 1.332-MeV of the pair, a 510.99-keV peak stemming from an annihilation of electron–positron pairs on the Pb or ^{60}Co or detector-crystal surfaces does not appear also.

The absence of both 1.173-MeV single- and double-escape peaks and the 510.99-keV annihilation peak signifies that the mechanism of the K line is another one.

Further, we elucidate the origin of the characteristic X ray for K line.

3.5. Conversion of 1.173-MeV-photon energy into $P_{\bar{S}}$ energy

The system consisting of the positron linking two electrons appears as energies E_{β^-} and E_{β^+} of created β^- and β^+ -rays, respectively, are diminished by energies, $E_{repulsion}$ and $E_{attraction}$, of repulsion and attraction of the K -shell electron, respectively, in a following manner:

$$(E_{\beta^-} - E_{repulsion}) - (E_{\beta^+} - E_{attraction}) + E_{K-shell-\beta} \equiv E_{3\beta}. \quad (3.17)$$

Here $E_{K-shell-\beta}$ is interaction energy of electron from K shell determined by a following formula:

$$E_{K-shell-\beta} = E_{\gamma} - [(E_{\beta^-} - E_{repulsion}) - (E_{\beta^+} - E_{attraction})], \quad (3.18)$$

$E_{repulsion}$ is the repulsion energy, $E_{attraction}$ is the attraction energy, which both have an opposite sign $E_{repulsion} > 0$, $E_{attraction} < 0$; $E_{\beta^-} > 0$ and $E_{\beta^+} < 0$, $E_{3\beta}$ is the interaction energy of the 3-body system, $E_{\beta^-} - E_{\beta^+} \approx 2m_e c^2$ due to the thermalization. Then, the energy of characteristic X ray for K line (E_{K-line}) is determined by the following equation:

$$E_{K-line} + E_{bind,shell} = E_{\gamma} - (E_{\beta^-} - E_{\beta^+}) + E_{gap} \equiv E_{K-shell-\beta} \quad (3.19)$$

where $E_{gap} = E_{repulsion} - E_{attraction}$ is a positronium energy gap. The K-shell-electron binding energy, $E_{bind,shell}$, for ^{60}Co is equal to

7.709 keV [29].

Accordingly to the internal-energy-conversion mechanism described above, the energy of 1.173-MeV photon is spent 1) to create the positronium-ion in the ground state when its lowest level are occupied by K-shell electron and positron e^+ and the electron from the created pair occupies upper energy level (see the upper picture from Fig. 3b, left) and 2) to excite the $e^+ - e^-_{K-shell}$ pair from the level E_0 to the level E_1 (see the upper picture from Fig. 3b, right). The characteristic X ray for K-line from the 1.173-MeV-energy conversion is determined as

$$E_{K-line} = E_{1.173-MeV} - [(E_{\beta^-} - E_{\beta^+}) - E_{gap} + E_{bind,shell}] \approx E_{1.173-MeV} - E_{bind,shell} - (2m_e c^2 - E_{gap}) \equiv E_{1.173-MeV} - E_{bind,shell} - E_{positronium}. \quad (3.20)$$

Here it is assumed that the kinetic energy of the pair is reduced to approximately thermal energy; $E_{positronium}$ is the positronium energy. According to formula (3.20), the formation of positronium increases the energy at which the K line is located. Theoretically, there is the K-line peak “X” in radiation spectrum for the ^{60}Co decay at an energy of $E_{K-line} = 143.3$ keV when $E_{gap} = 0$. Therefore, the experimental peak “X” at the energy of $E_{K-line}^{exper} = 147.19$ keV deposited in 71th channel of the ^{60}Co radiation response R_{Co} (see Table 1 and Figs. 1a) was attributed to the internal conversion of 1.173-MeV gamma ray both into the K line and the bound electron-positron pair under the condition that (in keV)

$$E_{gap} = E_{K-line}^{exper} - E_{K-line} = 3.89. \quad (3.21)$$

Experimentally, the energy expended to overcome the binding force and eject (or attract) an electron from the K shell is measured as (in keV)

$$E_{gap}^{exper} = E_{bind,shell} - E_{kin}^{exper} = 3.909. \quad (3.22)$$

This experimental value, E_{gap}^{exper} , is in nice

agreement with theoretical predictions (3.21) of E_{gap} . Prediction of E_{kin} which enters the expression (3.22) is that $E_{kin} = E_{bind,shell} - E_{gap} = 7.709 - 3.89 = 3.819$ keV. Since E_{kin}^{exper} from the expression (3.16) coincides with the theoretical value of E_{kin} , which is the energy of motion of the K-shell electron to the positron.

It is evidence of fact that the E_{gap} and E_{kin} energies of the K-shell electron moving around the positron from the electron-positron pair produced by the 1.173-MeV photon are potential and kinetic energies of the unexcited positronium, respectively. As a result, 1.173-MeV gamma-ray energy is not enough to excite the positronium. Correspondingly, the K-shell electron and the positron are located on the same orbital and move toward each other along unstable positronium orbitals of the pair ($e^+_{\downarrow, E_1} - e^-_{\downarrow, E_1}$) with non-zero energy, as shown in Fig. 3b. In the end, the positronium electron goes into the Dirac electron sea and, as a result, the positronium disappears. Therefore, E_{gap} can be interpreted as the energy of a force, tightening the

electron into the Dirac sea. After the annihilation between the K -shell electron and the positron, the released conversion electron e^- scatters on the atoms of the radioactive source that gives rise to the X -ray peak in the response function. The 1.173-MeV single and double escape annihilation peaks must be absent for the unstable ground state existing in this mechanism in full accord with the experimental evidences.

3.6. Internal energy conversion in ^{137}Cs nucleus decay

K -, L -, and M -line conversion-electron energies ($E_{e_i,con}, i = 1, 2, 3$) for $^{137\text{m}}\text{Ba}$ are of 624.2, 655.7, and 660.4 keV, respectively [30]. Correspondingly, since the ^{137}Cs -decay gamma-ray energy measured to date is of $E_{\gamma_v} = 661.657$ -keV [19], the K -, L -shell, and M -shell- electron binding energies ($E_i^{theor} \equiv E_{\gamma_v} - E_{e_i,con}$) should be of 37.457, 5.957, and 1.257-keV, respectively. Now, we can theoretically assess an energy, $E_{sum,conv}^{theor}$, deposited by the X -ray-summing event originated from the internal conversion of virtual E_{γ_v} photons at the $^{137\text{m}}\text{Ba}$ de-excitation as

$$E_{sum,conv}^{theor} = 2 \sum_{i=1}^3 E_i^{theor} = 89.34 \text{ keV}. \quad (3.23)$$

Here the factor of 2 takes into account the spin value of $\pm \frac{1}{2}$. The theoretical prediction (3.23) per one X ray of the order of

$$E_{sum,conv}^{theor}/3 = 29.74 \text{ keV}. \quad (3.24)$$

is as a value being nearest to an experimental value of 29.45-keV for the characteristic X ray which was along with 630-keV conversion electrons recorded by [31] in the (true) coincidence-summing event from the ^{137}Cs decay. But, the characteristic K -shell X rays with other 32-keV (K_α line) and 36-keV (K_β line) energies were also recorded along with the same 630-keV electrons for ^{137}Cs decay [32, 33] in the (true) coincidence summing. These experimental data is the evidence of the presence of transient electrons in nuclei.

Characteristic photons of K_β lines from lead (Pb) collimator have energies of 84.93 keV [34, 36] with the K -absorption edge of 88 keV [35, 36] is close to $E_{sum,conv}^{theor}$ (3.23). The last and very small internal-conversion coefficients complicate the detection of those true-coincidence summing events by the detector crystal and, correspondingly, mechanisms of internal conversion occurring in the radioactive ^{137}Cs decay.

3.6.1. Virtual P_S^- generation in ^{137}Cs nucleus decay

For a nuclear forbidden transition to occur during ^{137}Cs decay from the second excited $^{137\text{m}}\text{Ba}$ state with multipolarity “11/2-” to the state with multipolarity “3/2+”, four virtual gamma rays, $\gamma_i, i = 1, \dots, 4$, must be radiated by $^{137\text{m}}\text{Ba}$ in order to satisfy the law of angular-momentum conservation. The four virtual photons in electrical fields of atom-shell electrons can be produced three electron-positron pairs. The cascade event is pictured on Fig. 4a. Here, we make an assumption based on the comparison between $E_{sum,conv}^{theor}$ (3.23) and the experimental data [31–33] that the 630-keV conversion electrons appear due the capture of electrons in transient states and three emitted X -rays are involved in the (true) coincidence-summing event.

There appear three conversion electrons in the $^{137\text{m}}\text{Ba}$ transition from the neutral atomic state, $^{137\text{m}}\text{Ba}_{J=11/2}^0$, with the nuclear angular momentum, I , of 11/2 into an excited atomic state, $^{137}\text{Ba}_{J=3/2}^*$ with the angular nuclear momentum of 3/2 across an ionization atomic state, $^{137}\text{Ba}_{I=3/2}^{(+3)}$, with electrical charge of +3 as

$$\begin{aligned} ^{137\text{m}}\text{Ba}_{I=11/2}^0 &\equiv ^{137}\text{Ba}_{I=3/2}^0 + \sum_{i=1}^4 \gamma_i \\ &\rightarrow ^{137}\text{Ba}_{I=3/2}^{(+3)} + 3e_{shell,conversion}^- \end{aligned} \quad (3.25)$$

In this transition (3.25), the three atomic-shell conversion electrons, $3e_{shell,conversion}^-$, are expelled

after annihilating the created 3 electron-positron pairs. Subsequently, the appearing $^{137}\text{Ba}_{I=3/2}^*$ being comprised both by the Ba ion and 3 conversion electrons emits three X rays.

The forbidden $^{137\text{m}}\text{Ba}$ -nucleus transition from the second excited state to first ground one with an emission of four virtual γ photons satisfies the conservation law for angular momentum. Two virtual electron-positron pairs, $2(e^+ - e^-)$, produced by the four virtual γ photons in the heavy excited nucleus, interact with K - (L -, M -) shell electrons, $e_{K\text{shell}}^-$ ($e_{L\text{shell}}^-$, $e_{M\text{shell}}^-$), and the 661.7-keV photon from $e'^- - e'^+$ annihilation (see Fig. 3a) immediately excites the transition of the K -shell electron between the E_0 and E_1 levels. Then, after such interactions, a lower-energy positronium ion appears with zero-energy bound electron-positron pairs $e^+\uparrow, E_0 - e^-\downarrow, E_0$ (see Fig. 4) and, correspondingly, the pair production is really lacking (virtual).

An interaction with a vortical electrically charged graphene Dirac liquid may neutralize the positronium anion. The neutralization proceeds as the hole and electron currents, \vec{j}_V^+ and \vec{j}_V^- , originated from graphene pseudo-Majorana quasiparticle flow emerge. Level-energy diagrams both of the positronium charged and neutralized states are depicted in Fig. 4b.

The Coulomb interaction and quantum exchange confine the e_{\downarrow, E_0}^- and the graphene hole $h_{V, \downarrow}^+$ on an excited energy level E_0 of the P_S^- and simultaneously the transition of positron e^+ from the level E_0 into the energy level E_1 occurs under an action of an electrical field of the graphene electron e_{V, \uparrow, E_3}^- (see Fig. 4b). According to the neutralization mechanism, the electron e_{\downarrow, E_1}^- ($e_{\downarrow, E_1, K\text{-shell}}^-$) becoming conversion one after annihilation between e_{\downarrow, E_1}^+ and $e_{\uparrow, E_0, K\text{-shell}}^-$ (e_{\downarrow, E_1}^+ and $e_{\downarrow, E_0, K\text{-shell}}^-$) should acquire an additional energy equal to the energy gap E_{gap} of the bound electron-positron pair.

3.6.2. Intermediate-size-detector responses on photon beams of ^{137}Ce decay and detector calibration

Radiation spectra ^{137}Cs -decay presented in Fig. 4c were recorded during 5 minutes after 1-hour irradiation of the detector crystal.

They represent the detector response functions, from which the contribution due to the radiation background has been subtracted, the latter was also recorded during 5 minutes after 1-hour irradiation of the detector crystal. The coefficients of ^{137}Cs -IRS calibration over single-Compton-edge and 661.7-keV γ rays are with the following values:

$$a = 1.2, b = 3.4. \quad (3.26)$$

Neutralization of the positron ion by the graphene hole and electron currents \vec{j}_V^+ and \vec{j}_V^- (see Fig. 4b, bottom) diminish a number of electrically charged particles that are decelerated by the strong electric field near the nuclei. It means that the intensity of bremsstrahlung emitted by these particles falls down. The diminishing bremsstrahlung peak “*Brem*” in the detector response R_{CsG} in comparison with R_{Cs} is the evidence of the neutralization process (compare Figs. 4c, left and right).

Narrowing of the widths of the photopeak “*Ph*” and the peaks of characteristic “*X*” and backscattering “*BS*” from the detector response R_{CsG} in comparison with R_{Cs} increases the resolution of the detector.

In the radiation spectrum R_{CsG} there are two narrow X -ray-escape peaks, X_1 with a maximum at the 68th channel (at the energy of 85 keV) and X_2 with a maximum at the 74th channel (at the energy of 92.2 keV), instead of a single broad X -ray-escape peak, X , with a maximum at the 68th channel. Since the X_1 photon deposits 85-keV energy to the 68th channel, this event indicates, precisely, the characteristic X -ray radiation of lead. The (true) coincidence-summing event, detected by the peak X_2 , is the simultaneous X -rays emission depositing the total energy $E_{sum, conv}^{CNT-exper}$ of 92.2 keV. This value is close to the total binding

FIG. 4. (Color online) A model mechanism of internal energy conversion for an excited ^{137m}Ba nucleus (a) and energy-levels diagrams of positronium which appears in that virtual process proceeding without (b, up) and with graphene-currents impact (b, down). (c) Radiation spectra (c) were recorded for ^{137}Cs ionizing source by the detector system NaI(Tl)/rounded-up graphene (c, left) and the detector crystal only (c, right); the spectra were recorded during 5 min after 1-hour irradiation. The background radiation which was recorded during 5 min after 1-hour NaI(Tl)/graphene exposure to cosmic radiation was subtracted from the response functions on ^{137}Cs -decay γ rays.

energy (3.23) of the three atomic-shell electrons but does not coincide with it.

Our model predicts that the excess energy deposit is owing to the energy gap of bound electron–positron pair and our assessment gives its averaged value of order of $\langle E_{gap} \rangle = 3.85$ keV. Our experimental data testify for the internal energy conversion in a Ba nucleus that there are electrons being captured in transition processes from L -, M -shells and from an occupied level

and the nucleus-captured electrons are returned to vacancies in the atom shells immediately. Our experimental data testify to the internal energy conversion in a Ba nucleus, showing that electrons being captured in transition processes from the L - and M -shells and from an occupied level of the K shell to an unoccupied level of the K shell and nucleus-captured electrons return to the vacated positions in the atomic shells immediately. The nucleus-captured electrons are labeled as $e^-_{K\alpha}$,

$e_{K\beta}^-$, and $e_{K-shell}^-$ in Fig. 4a. It means that the atom missing an inner electron can relax by a cascade of X-ray emissions and, correspondingly, the true-coincidence summing event deposits the energy (in keV)

$$E_{sum,conv} = E_{sum,conv}^{CNT-exper} - \langle E_{gap} \rangle = 88.35 \quad (3.27)$$

As a result, an energy, E_t , for characteristic X ray equal to

$$E_t = \frac{1}{3} E_{sum,conv} = 29.45 \text{ keV} \quad (3.28)$$

is given by Eq. (3.27). It is very close to the theoretical value of 29.74 keV (see the formula (3.24)) and tallies exactly with the experimental value recorded by [31].

Thus, the energy gap of bound electron-positron pair is added to the total characteristic X-ray deposit into the channel of detection CNT/NaI(Tl) system. It means that three electrons from K -, L -, M - shells are confined with a higher binding energy due to an impact of electrical fields of graphene neutralizing currents which are excited by the ^{137}Ba γ radiation. The 661.7-keV internal conversion is affected by the graphene currents as the binding energy for three electrons from K -, L -, M - shells grows by E_{gap} and, as a result, the three conversion electrons escape with lower energies. The excess of energy of order 3.8–3.9 keV confirms the prediction of our model (see Fig. 4a and b) that there are interactions between vortical graphene currents and virtual positronium ions. When an electron-hole transfer emerges from the graphene conduction band into the positronium states the positron e^+ is relocated to the E_1 energy level and therefore generating the bound pair $e_{\downarrow,E_1}^+ - e_{\downarrow,E_1}^-$. Then the annihilation of $e_{\downarrow,E_1}^+ - e_{\uparrow,E_0,K-shell}^-$ leads to the ejection of conversion electron which energy is diminished by both the difference $E_1 - E_0$ and the additional binding energy of pair $e_{\uparrow,E_1}^+ - e_{\uparrow,E_1}^-$.

Thus, the proposed mechanism of internal energy conversion explains the appearance of the three characteristic X rays from the ^{137}Cs decay predicts theoretically the event as a cascade summing of pulses.

4. Discussion and conclusion

So, a detection system comprised by single-walled-CNT assemblies and detector crystal has been designed that allows to record cascade events. We revealed these events due to enhancement of decay-energy deposition by graphene walls of carbon nanotubes.

We offer mechanisms of internal conversion of γ -ray energy in ^{60}Co and ^{137}Cs decays. The mechanisms clarify the nature of the low-intensity peaks of radiation response functions for the ^{60}Co and ^{137}Cs decays and shed a light on a positronium generation giving rise to these peaks. We predict and experimentally confirm that electron and positron can reside both on the same energy level of the positronium ion and on different energy levels of the latter. Electron and positron with the same energy are linked. The bound positron-electron pair is unstable because of the forces pulling the electron back into the Dirac sea. The binding energy is attributed to the bound electron-positron pair as its energy gap because the latter is identical for both ^{60}Co and ^{137}Cs decays and does not depend on the γ -ray energy.

Let us discuss energies for states of the charged positronium configurations arising in ^{60}Ni nucleus. The energies are energies of photons produced by electron-positron annihilation, after that the attraction disappears and the centrifugal force carries a remaining electron away. Using this conjecture and supposing $E_0 = 0$ we can derive some positronium energy levels such as E_1 , E_2 , and E_3 . For the ^{60}Co decay, our calculations together with our experimental data testify that (in keV)

$$E_1 - E_0 \approx E_{K-line}^{exper} = 147, \quad (4.1)$$

$$E_2 = E_1 + (E_{sum} - E_{gap})/3 - E_0 \approx 249, \quad (4.2)$$

$$E_3 = E_2 + \left(E_{high-energy-P_S^-,4} - E_{high-energy-P_S^-} \right) - E_0 \approx 326. \quad (4.3)$$

Similarly, for the ^{137}Cs decay, $E_t = 29.45$ keV is the second excited energy level of virtual P_S^- .

We give evidence of the fact that γ rays from the radioactive decays are converted into positronium-ion entangled configurations with subsequent their destruction.

The proposed method of detecting radioactive decays based on CNT-enhanced

photon energy deposition in scintillating material opens prospects for studying rare nuclear processes when the observation of true coincidence events is masked by backscattering in the detector shielding or by the detector's generation of escaping X rays.

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